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**Research on Construction of Railway Financial Sharing System
Based on Business-Financial Integration**

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ABSTRACT

In order to adapt to the need of railway financial reform and innovation and to strengthen the railway financial management advantages and risk control ability, this paper studies the construction of railway financial sharing service system based on the theory of Business-financial integration. Combining the Business-financial integration with the construction of railway financial sharing service system, this paper puts forward the construction idea, design the organizational structure and analyze control mode of railway financial sharing service system. The key point is the overall structural design of railway financial sharing service system. And then specific implementation methods are given, finally explains the railway financial staff transformation development choice path. The purpose of this paper is to realize the integration of railway operation and finance and to improve the overall operation quality and efficiency of railway system.

INTRODUCTION

Railway financial shared construction is to integrate the repetitive and standardized financial business of all subordinate units of China Railway into the new business unit for unified processing to improve the railway financial management. It is feasible and necessary to construct railway financial sharing service system based on business-financial integration. From the perspective of objective conditions, the larger the enterprise size, the more incentive to establish financial sharing (Jing, 2020). Most financial shared service systems are established in large and medium-sized cities (Xuqiang, 2019). The basic units of the railway system are widely distributed, with large volume of business and strong repeatability. The office locations are concentrated in large and medium-sized cities (Chenglei, 2019), which provide site selection convenience for railway financial shared construction by virtue of their own resource advantages. From the perspective of management basis, railway operation managers have been increasingly conscious of operating benefits and timeliness of data is valued (Miao, 2018). The manager obtains the original data and business information through the railway financial sharing service platform to understand the operation status of the group in real time. The change of managers' conception of production over management and the need to strengthen internal management and improve economic efficiency are the driving force of railway financial sharing construction (Kuikui, 2020). From the practical basis, most foreign railway operating companies have established financial sharing system, as well as the domestic large enterprises similar to railway operation, which show strong management advantages and market operation ability (Liping, 2019). From the perspective of the inherent requirements of sustainable development of railways, the subordinate units of China Railway are positioned as "enterprise operation, market operation". According to this position, the railway subordinate units within the group need to establish a more standardized, scientific and

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reasonable financial organization structure. From the perspective of information technology reform, various management information systems in the railway system have begun to take shape, which has demonstrated effective financial management and other related effectiveness. However, full connectivity has not yet been achieved, and the ability to share services needs to be improved. The target of this paper is to integrate each financial management system to improve the overall efficiency of the railway. Therefore, combining business-financial integration with the construction of railway financial sharing service system makes the financial data statistics clear, promotes the upgrading and transformation of railway financial management mode, and implements the railway system theme of improve the quality and efficiency, strong base up to the standard.

Construction Thoughts

The construction of railway finance system should be guided by the theory of Information enablement theory to solve the problem of railway value creation. Managers create shared visions within the railway system. The workflow is event-driven. The railway shared financial system integrates various objectives, promotes the integration of finance and business within the railway system, breaks the information barrier, optimizes allocation of resources, and combines process control with management efficiency and effectiveness.

Specifically, to carry out the construction of railway financial sharing service system based on the intelligent financial concept, the basic idea should meet the points. Firstly, the service operation process should be more efficient and flexible. Secondly, it should be further improved of the support function of railway financial sharing data for railway management decision. Thirdly, railway financial staff evolved from physical concentration to regional virtual set. Fourthly, railway operation management mode will be Outsourcing and crowdsourcing. Lastly, railway services will operate in a more integrated manner.

Organization Design

Organization Structure

According to the railway business, financial shared was set as five business accounting departments, which include income undergraduate, general accounting section, asset expense section, fund settlement section and statements tax section, and three operation departments, which include operations management section, supervision and audit section and data asset management section. Its organizational structure is shown in figure 1.

Fig. 1. Organization structure

Organization structure of Financial Sharing

Management-control Model

The business accounting department is responsible for the business process accounting of each department, review business original documents, evaluate internal accounting policy, accounting system and accounting rules, put forward the optimization scheme of accounting process, and organize management system publicity and training. Operation department is responsible for accounting management of financial sharing construction and daily operation and maintenance of information system, and propose standard scheme of business processing. In order to achieve strategic synergy, China Railway puts forwards strategic decision. And each subordinate unit provides business performance to the group. The financial Shared Service system plays the role of service execution. The financial control mode is shown in figure 2.

Fig 2. The financial control mode

Structure Design

Extensional Organization

In the system construction process of railway financial shared, the data interface is established to break through the "data island", and the system process is reworked to form the railway financial shared service based on business-financial integration. This paper establishes railway financial supervision system, checks all date, and improves the tax administration system. Tax work is done through the business and management information technology platform. Data sharing and transmission is realized by integrating various data through data of the fund system, financial shared system and online banking interface of commercial bank. The overall design of railway financial sharing construction is shown in figure 3.

Fig 3. Overall Design of Financial Sharing Construction for RAILWAY

Manner of Implementation

There are two ways to promote the integration of business and finance, which are the top design and the bottom promotion. China Railway chooses the top design. Firstly, system integration design is carried out, and then the old business system and financial system are transformed into the business and financial integration mode system. The implementation of railway business-financial integration has realized integration of operational action, expense reimbursement, fund settlement and accounting treatment and the integration between China Railway and its affiliated units. Taking railway bureau as an example, implementation design of integration of business and finance is shown in figure 4.

Fig. 4. Implementation design of Integration of Business and Finance

Conclusion

The construction of railway financial shared service system is an important content of railway financial reform and innovation and is the only way to promote the transformation of railway finance. The construction of railway financial sharing service system is to integrate the repetitive and standardized financial business of all subordinate units of China Railway into the new business unit for unified processing, to promote business and financial integration of China Railway, and to accelerate the reform of railway finance. There are three parts of the construction of railway financial sharing service system, which includes standardization system specification, operation management specification and user operation specification. The railway traditional financial staff will be

transformed into financial shared staff, business finance staff and risk managers. On the one hand, the construction of railway financial shared service system will effectively integrate various data and realize the resource sharing within the railway. At the same time, it will effectively control operating costs, improve financial processing efficiency and data quality, and reduce railway operation risk. On the other hand, the construction of railway financial sharing service system needs more powerful information technology system to break through the functional management mode of the organization department. In the future, the functional scope of railway sharing service system construction will not be limited to the financial field. It will have more features, such as human resources, information technology, customer contact center and law works.

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